

METAL SULFIDE NANO-MATERIALS: SYNTHESIS, PREPARATION, PROPERTIES, AND POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Metal sulfides (MSs) nanomaterials have become increasingly popular due to their extensive range of applications in various fields, such as medicine, biology, environmental sciences, and energy production/utilization. The light absorption, optical characteristics, high specific capacitance, and catalytic/photocatalytic capability of MSs nanomaterials make them ideal for these applications. In medicine, MSs nanomaterials can be used for enhanced imaging, drug delivery, and cancer therapy due to their light absorption and optical characteristics. These nanomaterials have also been used in biosensors, biosynthesis, and bio-imaging. In environmental sciences, MSs nanomaterials have been used for water treatment, pollutant detection, and remediation due to their high specific capacitance. In energy production/utilization, MSs nanomaterials have been explored for hydrogen production, solar energy conversion, and catalytic/photocatalytic conversion due to their catalytic/photocatalytic capability. Overall, MSs nanomaterials are prospective candidates for multidimensional applications in medicine, biology, environmental sciences, and energy production/utilization due to their light absorption, optical characteristics, high specific capacitance, and catalytic/photocatalytic capability. Their potential for a multitude of applications makes MSs nanomaterials an attractive option for researchers and scientists. In this review we discussed on types of metal sulfide, preparation of metal sulfide and application of metal sulfide.

Keywords: Metal sulfides, nanomaterials, biosynthesis, environmental sciences

1. INTRODUCTION

The demand for removing drugs from materials continues to increase, making metal sulfide a highly valuable and sought-after resource in this field. Its unique properties make it particularly beneficial for drug removal, as it has the ability to bind to many molecules, including a variety of drugs. This makes it both cost-effective and efficient for drug removal [1]. Metal sulfide also has a wide range of applications, such as in medical, agricultural, and industrial settings. Additionally, it can be used in various forms, including powder, granules, and pellets. This versatility makes it suitable for a variety of drug removal needs. As the demand for drug removal continues to grow, metal sulfide is likely to play a crucial role in this rapidly expanding market. Nanostructured metal sulfides have been extensively studied in the past decade due to their importance in interpreting quantum size effects and applications in modern devices [2]. These nanostructured metal sulfides are being used in a variety of devices, such as solar cells, light-emitting diodes, sensors, thermoelectric devices, lithium-ion batteries, fuel cells and nonvolatile memory devices. The quantum size effects of nanostructured metal sulfides have made them especially attractive for use in these devices, as they are able to increase the efficiency and performance of the device. Moreover, they are lightweight, cost-effective, and durable, which makes them ideal for use in a variety

of applications [3]. Furthermore, nanostructured metal sulfides are also attractive for use in biomedical devices, as they can be used to create highly sensitive sensors and detectors. The research and development of nanostructured metal sulfides are ongoing, and the applications of these materials are becoming increasingly diverse [4]. Metal sulfides are a major group of minerals that show a wide variety of structural types and are abundant and relatively inexpensive. Heazlewoodite (Ni₃S₂), chalcocite (Cu₂S), and pyrite (FeS₂) are all examples of naturally occurring metal sulfides. In addition, many metal sulfide nanostructure arrays can be synthesized in the laboratory [5]. Such nanostructures include ZnS, Cu₂S, Ni₃S₂, and Co₉S₈, to name a few. Due to the wide variety of structures, metal sulfides are a popular choice for research in crystal chemistry. The abundance and low cost of these materials make them an attractive option for many applications [1-5]. In this review we discussed on types of metal sulfide, preparation of metal sulfide and application of metal sulfide.

2. METAL SULFIDES

Metal sulfides are a class of chemical compounds that consist of a metal element bonded to sulfur. They are

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formed by the combination of a metal cation (positively charged metal ion) and a sulfide anion (negatively charged sulfur ion). Metal sulfides can exist as minerals in nature or can be synthesized in the laboratory. In metal sulfides, the metal atom or ion acts as a central atom, surrounded by sulfur atoms. The ratio of metal to sulfur atoms can vary, leading to different stoichiometries. For example, iron sulfide (FeS) has a 1:1 ratio of iron to sulfur atoms, while zinc sulfide (ZnS) has a 1:1 ratio of zinc to sulfur atoms. Metal sulfides can exhibit a wide range of properties depending on the specific metal and the nature of the bonding between metal and sulfur. They can have various colors, from metallic gray or silver to yellow, brown, or even black. Some metal sulfides, such as iron sulfide (pyrite), can have a metallic luster. Metal sulfides have important applications in different fields. They can be used as catalysts in chemical reactions, as semiconductors in electronic devices, as pigments in paints and dyes, and as raw materials for metal extraction. Examples of commonly known metal sulfides include pyrite (iron sulfide), galena (lead sulfide), sphalerite (zinc sulfide), and cinnabar (mercury sulfide) [2]. Different kinds of metal sulfides are shown in figure 1.

Figure 1 Different example of metal sulfide [2]

Types of metal sulfide

Composites of metal sulfides refer to materials that combine metal sulfide compounds with other substances to enhance their properties or create new functionalities. These composites often exhibit improved mechanical, electrical, thermal, or chemical characteristics compared to the individual components. Here are a few examples of composites involving metal sulfides are shown in figure 2.

Metal Sulfide-Polymer Composites

Metal sulfide nanoparticles or powders can be incorporated into polymer matrices to create composite materials. These composites can offer enhanced mechanical strength, improved thermal stability, and increased resistance to chemical degradation. They find applications in areas such as coatings, sensors, and flexible electronics [3].

Metal Sulfide-Carbon Composites

Combining metal sulfides with carbon-based materials like graphene or carbon nanotubes can lead to composites with exceptional electrical and thermal conductivity. These composites have potential applications in energy storage devices, catalysis, and electronic devices [4].

Metal Sulfide-Metal Oxide Composites

Metal sulfide nanoparticles or nanowires can be combined with metal oxide materials to form composites with tailored properties. These composites often exhibit enhanced photocatalytic activity, making them useful for applications in solar cells, water purification, and environmental remediation [5].

Metal Sulfide-Ceramic Composites

Metal sulfide particles or fibers can be incorporated into ceramic matrices to improve their mechanical strength, toughness, and thermal shock resistance. These composites are used in applications such as cutting tools, wear-resistant coatings, and high-temperature components [6].

Metal Sulfide-Glass Composites

Metal sulfide nanoparticles can be dispersed within a glass matrix to create composites with unique optical properties. These composites find applications in areas such as optics, photonics, and display technologies.

Figure 2 Different types of metal sulfides material [7]

The specific properties and applications of metal sulfide composites depend on the choice of metal sulfide, the matrix material, and the fabrication techniques used to produce the composite. By tailoring the composition and structure, researchers can design composites with desired functionalities for various industrial and technological applications

Preparation of metal sulfides

The preparation of metal sulfides can vary depending on the specific metal and sulfide compound involved. Here are a few common methods for preparing metal sulfides:

Direct Reaction Method

This method involves the direct reaction of a metal with a sulfur source to form the metal sulfide. The metal and sulfur source can be heated together in a controlled atmosphere, such as hydrogen sulfide gas (H₂S), sulfur vapor, or elemental sulfur. The reaction typically takes place at elevated temperatures. For example, iron sulfide (FeS) can be prepared by heating iron and sulfur together [8].

Solvothermal/Hydrothermal Method

In this method, metal salts or precursors are dissolved in a suitable solvent along with a sulfur source, such as thioacetamide or thiourea. The reaction mixture is then heated in a sealed container at high temperatures and pressures. This allows for the controlled formation of metal sulfide nanoparticles or crystals. The choice of solvent and reaction conditions can influence the size, morphology, and properties of the resulting metal sulfide [9].

Chemical Precipitation Method

Metal sulfides can be prepared through chemical precipitation by mixing metal salts with a sulfide ion source. Commonly used sulfide sources include sodium sulfide (Na₂S), hydrogen sulfide gas (H₂S), or sodium hydrosulfide (NaHS). The metal salt solution is gradually mixed with the sulfide ion source, leading to the formation of metal sulfide precipitates. The precipitates can then be collected, washed, and dried [10].

Sol-Gel Method

This method involves the hydrolysis and condensation of metal alkoxides or metal salts in the presence of a sulfur-containing compound. The precursor solution undergoes a gelation process, resulting in the formation of a metal-sulfur gel. Subsequent drying and calcination steps lead to the formation of the desired metal sulfide material [11].

Vapor Deposition Methods

Metal sulfides can also be prepared using vapor deposition techniques, such as chemical vapor deposition (CVD) or physical vapor deposition (PVD). In CVD, metal organic precursors and sulfur-containing gases are introduced into a reaction chamber and undergo decomposition or reaction on a heated substrate to deposit the metal sulfide film. PVD techniques involve the physical evaporation or sputtering of a metal target in the presence of sulfur, resulting in the deposition of metal sulfide thin films [12].

These are just a few examples of the methods used to prepare metal sulfides. The choice of method depends on factors such as the desired properties, particle size, morphology, and intended application of the metal sulfide material.

Applications of metal sulfides

Metal sulfides are important for various reasons, including their wide range of applications, their natural occurrence, and their role in various industrial processes. Here are some key reasons why metal sulfides are significant and application of FeS shown in figure 3.

Metal sulfides occur naturally as minerals and are often major sources of valuable metals. For example, metal sulfides such as galena (lead sulfide), chalcopyrite (copper iron sulfide), and sphalerite (zinc sulfide) are important ores for lead, copper, and zinc extraction, respectively. These minerals are crucial for the production of metals used in various industries, including construction, electronics, and transportation. Several metal sulfides exhibit semiconducting properties, making them essential materials for electronic devices. Metal sulfides like cadmium sulfide (CdS) and zinc sulfide (ZnS) are commonly used as semiconductors in photovoltaic cells,

light-emitting diodes (LEDs), and sensors. They possess unique optoelectronic properties, such as bandgap tunability, high absorption coefficients, and efficient charge transport, making them vital for renewable energy technologies and lighting applications. Metal sulfides play a critical role as catalysts in various chemical reactions. They are employed in processes such as hydrodesulfurization (HDS) in the petroleum industry, where they help remove sulfur impurities from crude oil and convert them into hydrogen sulfide. Metal sulfide catalysts also find applications in the production of chemicals, such as methanol synthesis, Fischer-Tropsch synthesis, and hydrogen production. Their catalytic properties enable efficient and selective reactions, leading to improved process efficiency and reduced environmental impact. Metal sulfides have shown promise as electrode materials in energy storage devices. For example, transition metal sulfides, including iron sulfides (FeS_x) and cobalt sulfides (CoS_x), have been investigated for applications in lithium-ion batteries, sodium-ion batteries, and supercapacitors. These materials offer high specific capacities, excellent electrochemical stability, and cost advantages, making them potential alternatives to conventional electrode materials. Certain metal sulfides possess unique optical properties, such as high refractive indices, excellent transparency in the infrared range, and strong nonlinear optical effects. These properties make them valuable for applications in optics and photonics. Metal sulfides are used in the fabrication of optical fibers, infrared windows, lenses, and photonic devices like waveguides, lasers, and photodetectors. Metal sulfides find applications in environmental remediation and pollution control. They can be utilized for the removal of heavy metals from wastewater through processes like adsorption and precipitation. Metal sulfides also exhibit photocatalytic activity, which can be harnessed for the degradation of organic pollutants in water and air purification [1-6].

Figure 3 Application of FeS in different field

These are just a few examples highlighting the importance of metal sulfides. Their unique properties and versatile applications make them valuable in various industries, contributing to technological advancements, resource

extraction, energy storage, and environmental sustainability

3. CONCLUSION

Metal sulfide nanostructures have attracted considerable attention due to their unique properties and potential applications in energy conversion and storage. In this overview, we discuss the synthesis, properties, and future promising areas of metal sulfide nanostructures, with a focus on their electronic, optoelectronic, magnetic, piezoelectric, and electrochemical devices.

The synthesis of metal sulfides involves a variety of techniques, such as solution-based methods, hydrothermal synthesis, and electrochemical deposition. Depending on the method of synthesis, the structures of the resulting nanostructures can range from nanorods to nanowires and nanotubes. The properties of the metal sulfides are strongly influenced by their structure and composition. Their electronic properties include bandgap, carrier mobility, and temperature-dependent conductivity. Optical properties include photo-induced absorption, fluorescence, and photoluminescence. Magnetic properties include magnetism, coercivity, and remanence. Piezoelectric properties include piezoelectric coefficient, dielectric constant, and piezoelectric response.

In terms of applications, metal sulfides have been explored for use in lithium-ion batteries, fuel cells, and solar cells. They have also been proposed as potential materials for use in electrochemical capacitors, electrochemical sensors, and photocatalytic water splitting. Metal sulfides have also been used as protective coatings for metals and alloys.

In conclusion, metal sulfide nanostructures offer a wide range of properties and applications in energy conversion and storage. Their synthesis, properties, and applications are the focus of ongoing research, and there are promising future applications of these materials.

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